

Hematosalpinx Revealed by Ovarian Torsion: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT/SUMMARY

Hematosalpinx is defined as the dilation of the uterine tube filled with blood, and it is a rare condition in children with multiple potential causes, including secondary to ovarian torsion. We present a case of hematosalpinx discovered due to ovarian torsion in a 14-year-old female with no prior medical history. She was admitted for acute, non-febrile right iliac fossa pain that had started two days prior to admission. Clinical examination revealed tenderness in the right iliac fossa. Infectious work up yielded negative results, and ultra sound examination revealed ovarian torsion with compromised blood supply to the right ovary. Surgical exploration revealed a twisted mass involving the right fallopian tube with a compromised right ovary, while the left side appeared normal. The patient underwent salpingectomy with preservation of the right ovary, and histopathological analysis confirmed the diagnosis of hematosalpinx. The patient had a favorable outcome after a 4-month follow-up period.

Keywords: Hematosalpinx; Ovary; Surgery; torsion.

INTRODUCTION

Ovarian torsion is a rare condition that can occur at any age, from the fetal period to adulthood.^[1,2] It can be particularly severe in children. It results from the spontaneous rotation of the vascular and lymphatic pedicle of the adnexa around its axis, which can lead to hemorrhagic infarction.^[3] It can occur on a healthy ovary or more frequently on a previously pathological ovary.^[1,2] It is a surgical emergency, and its diagnosis remains challenging due to the nonspecific clinical presentation. However, prompt diagnosis is crucial to preserve the patient's life, ovarian function, and fertility. Abdominopelvic ultra sound with Doppler is the preferred and necessary imaging modality in emergencies to approach the diagnosis of ovarian torsion, although it may not confirm it definitively. Surgical exploration remains the key to diagnosis. The use of laparoscopy and conservative approaches are currently the preferred methods to preserve ovarian tissue as much as possible. We report a case of clinically and

radiologically suspected ovarian torsion with the discovery of a twisted tubal mass and a compromised right ovary, suggesting a diagnosis of hematosalpinx.

CASE REPORT

We present the case of a 14-year-old girl with no previous medical history who presented with acute intense pain in the right iliac fossa. The pain was non-febrile and had started two days prior to admission. The patient did not report any gastro intestinal or urinary symptoms, and there were no other associated signs. Up on clinical examination, the girl appeared conscious, asthenic, pale, stable, and afebrile. The abdomen was soft and non-distended, with tenderness in the right iliac fossa and an intact hymen.

Infectious workup, including white blood cells count (8000) and C-reactive protein (CRP), was negative. The beta-human chorionic gonadotropin (BHCG) and alpha-fetoprotein (AFP) levels were also negative. The diagnostic evaluation was completed with an abdominal ultrasound, which revealed dilated right fallopian tube with a whirlpool sign and a heterogeneous right ovary with preserved Doppler flow. A computed tomography scan (CT scan) confirmed the findings of the ultrasound. Surgical exploration revealed a twisted right tubal mass with a compromised right ovary, while the left side appeared normal. Our therapeutic approach involved salpingectomy with preservation of the right ovary. The histopathological examination confirmed the diagnosis of hematosalpinx, with no evidence of villous cells or suspicious lesions. The patient had a good recovery after a 4-month follow-up period.

DISCUSSION

Ovarian torsion is an exceptional cause of pelvic pain in women and adolescents, with a prevalence of 1 in 1.5 million women. Approximately 350 cases have been reported in the literature, presenting with a similar clinical picture as tubal torsion. It predominantly affects the right side for the same reasons as ovarian torsion.^[4] Reported ultrasound signs include a normal uterus and ovaries with a dilated tube or a lateral-uterine mass corresponding to the twisted tube.^[5] It is a surgical emergency that relies on laparoscopy. Salpingectomy with preservation of the ovary is irreversible in case of tubal necrosis. A salvaging procedure has been described only once in the literature by Kurzbart et al.^[4,6]

In adolescents, several causes have been proposed, including increased tubal spiraling during ovulation, menstruation, and pregnancy, long mesosalpinx and mesovarium, tubal peristalsis, sudden positional changes, pelvic adhesions, and tubal ligation.^[4] Pathologies such as paratubal cysts, hematosalpinx, and hydrosalpinx can also be the underlying cause of torsion.^[4,7]

The most common immediate postoperative complication is fever, which easily resolves with antipyretics, especially after conservative treatment. It is explained by the resorption of necrosis.^[8,9] Long-term monitoring is based on clinical examination and ultrasound 6 to 8 weeks after the intervention, particularly in patients who underwent conservative treatment.^[10] The restoration of normal flow can take 2 to 6 months.^[9] Some authors recommend performing a second laparoscopy a few months apart.^[10]

Prevention of ovarian torsion is achieved by hormonal treatment of large ovarian cysts to prevent their torsion.

Figure 1: Intraoperative view showing the twisted tubal mass with a compromised right ovary.

Figure 2: CT scan sections showing the compromised appearance of the ovary and the right fallopian tube.

CONCLUSION

Hematosalpinx and ovarian torsion are rare and serious conditions in children. Their clinical presentation mimics several other pathologies, including appendicitis, as no signs are specific. Abdominopelvic ultrasound with color Doppler is an essential examination in emergency settings to explore abdominal pain of this nature, as it maintains a high diagnostic accuracy. Laparoscopic surgical exploration is the method of choice for confirming the positive diagnosis and performing the necessary surgical intervention. Conservative treatment through detorsion is recommended, despite the presence of ovarian ischemia. Post operative follow-up is based on clinical examination and ultrasound to confirm the recovery of ovarian function, which can be observed in approximately 91% of detorsion cases.

REFERENCES

1. C Veyrac, R Perez, C Baud, A Couture, M Saguintaah. Les douleurs pelviennes de la petite fille et de l'adolescente: l'imagerie diagnostique dans la pratique quotidienne. Feuilles De Radiologie, 2002;42, n°6,463-472.

2. M Balu, A Tarrant, M Lenoir, H Ducou Le Pointe. Imagerie des masses ovariennes avant la pubertéOvarian masses imaging before puberty. 2008;15:783-5.
3. Lawrence G Davis, Eugenio O Gerscovich, Mark W Anderson, Robin Stading. Anderson, Robin Stading. Ultrasound and Doppler in the diagnosis of ovarian torsion. European journal of Radiology. 1995;20:133-6.
4. F Cuillier, JC. Sommer Torsion tubaire isolée chez une adolescente de 15 ans .Arch PCdiatr 2000;7:748-51.
5. Megan Gross, Sylvie L Blumstein, Lawrence C Chow. Isolated Fallopian Tube Torsion: A Rare Twist on a Common Theme. AJR Am J Roentgenol . 2005;185(6):1590-2.
6. M F Brown, A Hebra , K McGeehin ,AJ Ross. Ovarian masses in children: a review of 91 cases of malignant and benign masses. J Pediatr Surg. 1993;28(7):930-3.
7. L Darrell Cass. Ovarian torsion. Semin Pediatr Surg . 2005;14(2):86-92.
8. EL GHRABLI.M le traitement laparoscopique des torsions d'annexe chez l'enfant : A propos de 12 cas.these de medecine n°99/2012.
9. Ahmet Celik, Orkan Ergun, Hakan Aldemir, CosSkun Ozcan, Geylani Ozok, Ata Erdener, et al. Long-term results of conservative management of adnexal torsion in children . J Pediatr Surg. 2005;40(4):704-8.
10. F Meynol, H Steyaert, JS Valla. [Adnexal torsion in children: plea for early laparoscopic diagnosis and treatment].Arch Pediatr. 1997;4:416-419.